

Research Article

Viking body-making: new evidence for intra-action with iconic Viking anthropomorphic ‘art’

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In Viking archaeology, the study of miniature figurines cast in silver and bronze provides a platform for debates on ritual and mythology, yet much of this discourse focuses on their appearance. Here, the authors use microwear and Reflective Transformation Imaging to survey the physical evidence of complex relational dynamics between 10 anthropomorphic artefacts from Viking Age Sweden and the human bodies they connected with. Through such analyses, and the abandonment of *a priori* assumptions regarding their purpose and symbolism, these figures can be seen as more than just components of an imposed category, and their varied, transmutable engagements with the world can be explored more freely.

Keywords: Scandinavia, Sweden, Viking Age, microwear analysis, Reflective Transformation Imaging, Old Norse religion

Introduction

Anthropomorphic ‘art’ from the deep past continues to capture our imagination. In Viking (*c.* AD 750–1050) archaeology, body-imagery generates numerous questions, including: what do these anthropomorphic figures symbolise? Do objects represent mythological beings or Norse gods known from later written sources? Can they be mapped onto a familiar cast of Viking warriors, kings and ritual specialists? Yet, fascination with anthropomorphic imagery can be “dangerously seductive” (Weismantel & Meskell 2014: 234). The scholarly gaze can become so mesmerised by the symbolic that other forms of inquiry are overshadowed (Back Danielsson 2013; Bailey 2014;

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Weismantel 2014). Scandinavian body-imagery has arguably fallen into taxonomic prisons (cf. Back Danielsson 2013; Eriksen 2022), where fixation on the identification of specific deities or categories obscures other knowledge potentials, which may rather emerge through an increased focus on the making, creative choices, engagement with and deposition of anthropomorphic artefacts.

This article builds from, and develops new answers to, such critiques. It seeks, for the first time, to examine these iconic Viking artefacts through microwear analysis and Reflective Transformation Imaging (RTI) to explore their engagement (making, use and breakage). This approach shifts the gaze from the familiar to the unfamiliar—from visual representation to past intra-action—through detailed examination of the objects and the worlds from which they emerged.

Body-worlding: concepts, objectives and methods

When people in the past chose to cast a human body in metal miniatures, they could not do so neutrally, detached from the politics, beliefs and material worlds they were situated within. Thus, Viking Age anthropomorphic pendants and figurines were entwined with, for example, contemporaneous global metal trade networks and remelted dirhams; circulating concepts of the body, gender and sexuality; Norse ideas of the otherworld; and the skills of their makers. Here, we employ the working concepts of ‘body-worlding’ (Haraway 1997; Eriksen 2022) and ‘intra-action’ (Barad 2007). “Nothing comes without its world, so knowing that world is crucial” (Haraway 1997: 137); rather than seeing ‘art’ objects as detached and passive, we forefront the links, connections and interdependencies of artefacts—their ‘worlding’. In this case, we are specifically interested in how bodies—human and metal—engaged one another. This approach is more-than-representational (cf. Back Danielsson 2013; Harris 2018); we do not deny the value of representational approaches focused on symbolism and meaning, but understand representation as one of many ways artefacts acted in, and gave shape to, body-worlds.

We see body-worlding as a verb (rather than a noun, cf. Robb & Harris 2013), a set of actions emerging from engagement and intra-action. Intra-action (Barad 2007), now an established concept in archaeology (e.g. Alberti & Marshall 2014), captures complex, relational dynamics between forces, rather than dividing the world *a priori* into subjects and objects. In the case of figurative ‘art’, thinking with body-worlding and intra-action allows us to focus on the encounters, links and entwinements among human and metal bodies, rather than assuming their predetermined qualities based on prior categorisation stemming from our own, late capitalist world (e.g. subject/object, maker/product).

Objectives and methods

The core objectives of this study are twofold. First, to empirically interrogate the engagements anthropomorphic objects elicited and the practices in which they may have been caught up. By looking to traces of attachment, handling or manipulation we ask, in what ways did these iconic Viking Age objects intra-act with the world? The article

thus examines traces of engagement, use and breakage through macro- and microscopic analytic approaches from a theoretically engaged perspective.

The second objective, explicitly relating to Viking Age discourse but with transferable value, is to trouble the way in which scholarship has enforced gender and other categorisation in the interpretation of these artefacts. For example, so-called ‘valkyrie pendants’—anthropomorphic figures conventionally interpreted as mythical female beings who guided fallen warriors to the deathrealm Valhalla—have been *assumed* to be worn by women (see discussion below). We aim to take a step back from the familiar, comfortable categories Viking Age scholarship often reverts to (binary-gendered worlds of housewives, kings and warriors; cf. Arwill-Nordbladh 2013a; Marshall *et al.* in press) and think anew about these miniature metal bodies. What happens if we stop forcing artefacts into our categories, and instead let them show us how they engaged with tools, hands and spaces—how they changed over time, demanded attention, were broken and remade?

Towards the fulfilment of these objectives, we employ two methods: microwear analysis and RTI (see online supplementary materials (OSM1–3) for additional detail). Microwear analysis is the macro- and microscopic study of traces that develop on the surface of objects during their manufacture, handling, use and post-depositional taphonomy. Primarily this analysis is applied to the study of tools and ornaments (e.g. van Gijn 2010; Crellin 2018), and to a limited extent to figural objects (e.g. Bider *et al.* 2014). Objects were subjected to low power microscopic wear analysis (up to 50× magnification) using a stereomicroscope (Nikon Nissho Optical) and micrographs were taken using a Dino-Lite Universal Digital Microscope and DinoCapture 2.0 software. Recorded wear traces include linear features (striations, troughs), surface modification (percussive traces, abraded areas) and deformation of perforation rim (facets, edge rounding).

RTI captures surface topography through photography and computational processing, recording three-dimensional reflectance properties of object surfaces. Objects were photographed with a light source positioned at different angles, and the images processed to reveal surface details at enhanced visibility. Application of raking light and alternative surface renderings can help determine details in decoration, manufacturing processes and post-manufacture interaction (e.g. Jones & Díaz-Guardamino 2019; Min *et al.* 2021).

Iconic Viking anthropomorphic figures

Ten iconic silver and bronze anthropomorphic objects (O1–O10) from the Viking Age exhibition of the Swedish History Museum were selected for analysis (Figures 1 & 2; see OSM4 for full details). These include seven full-figured anthropomorphs (‘valkyries’), a seated, phallic figure, a disembodied head and a circular figure with a protruding belly (the latter constituting the only convincing Viking Age depiction of a pregnant body; Eriksen *et al.* 2025). These objects feature prominently in discourse on Viking mythology, ritual and gender (Arwill-Nordbladh 2012; Helmbrecht 2013; Price 2019; Gardęła *et al.* 2022). So-called ‘valkyries’ are found in Scandinavia and beyond (see Figure S1) (we examined six of 18 existing Type 1 ‘valkyries’; see OSM4), while other

Figure 1. Ten iconic anthropomorphic objects from the Viking Age (figure by authors; images by O. Myrin, Swedish Historical Museums, CC BY 4.0).

objects are singular—thus also capturing the interplay between type-like and unique objects. While far from an exhaustive dataset, these examples provide a solid foundation for the inaugural application of these methods to anthropomorphic ‘art’ from the Viking Age, which can be augmented by future studies.

Eight objects are antiquarian, and of these three were stray finds (Table 1). As such, our understanding of the taphonomic and depositional processes that affected these objects is limited, as is our awareness of conservation histories for the objects, which can impact the interpretation of microwear. Yet, our analyses demonstrate that even with limited knowledge of object biographies, asking new kinds of questions can generate new knowledge. As most such objects in the wider Viking corpus are found through metal-detecting (Pentz 2018), they are likely characterised by similar issues. Thus, this

Figure 2. Map showing distribution of the artefacts (figure by K. Eriksen).

are recorded in the museum catalogue as depicting ‘valkyries’, yet variation in iconography and material raises questions over whether the objects constitute a single motif. Homogenising typologies may bring implicit presuppositions about homogeneity of use.

Second, and consequently, each object has been assumed to have a symbolic-magical purpose or to constitute an ‘amulet’ (Table 1). Two objects (O1 & O2) have been interpreted as ritual paraphernalia for an Old Norse *völva*, a female ritual specialist (Price 2019: 103–104). Third, all objects except O3 are characterised as body adornments (e.g. Plochov 2007) and are assumed to have been worn by women. For example, in their otherwise innovative article on digital reconstruction of figurine moulds, Deckers and colleagues (2021: 52–53) assume rather than argue that ‘valkyrie’ pendants were worn by “women ... on ceremonial occasions ... emphasis[ing] their role and status”. This is despite the fact that only two of the six ‘valkyries’ discussed here were found in burials that potentially also contained the skeletal remains of female individuals (which, in itself, is not conclusive evidence for gender-specific wear in life). Moreover, if the figures do depict valkyries who guided warriors to Valhalla, would we not expect that male warriors could also wear them? Assumptions of body adornment as inherently ‘feminine’ may be bleeding into these interpretations (O’Sullivan 2015).

Scholarship has generally been preoccupied with gendering late-prehistoric Scandinavian anthropomorphic art through a representational framing, despite the lack of primary sexual characteristics on most figures (cf. Arwill-Nordbladh 2013a). This has generated interpretative guidelines such as, for example: ‘women often had hair that was

study may work as a model for teasing out new information from decontextualised artefacts.

Previous interpretations

While representational approaches provide invaluable insight into the symbolism and ritual power of anthropomorphic objects (e.g. Arwill-Nordbladh 2012; Helmbrecht 2013; Price 2019), we focus here on their more-than-representational qualities, specifically the material traces of intra-actions. A preoccupation with visual symbolism has, we argue, led to three core assumptions about these iconic objects. First, each of the 10 objects studied here has, in scholarship or curatorial cataloguing, been connected with mythological beings from later written sources (e.g. Thor, Freya, Mimir, valkyries) or with aristocratic housewives and warriors (see OSM4). Objects O5–O10 are

Table 1. Overview of results.

	Previous interpretation	Multistaged manufacture?	Polish	Attachment	Microwear	Breakage/mending	Deposition
O1	Mimir's head; mount for <i>völva</i> staff/ magical paraphernalia	Y	Mostly polished	Loop (head)	Possible rubbing/handling of chin; Suspension wear (loop)	Intentional percussion to sever head; Postdepositional (?) hairline fracture to loop	Cremation burial (remains determined as female on unknown grounds)
O2	Freya; magical paraphernalia	Y	Obverse: mostly polished; Reverse: polished	Loops (head)	Facets (loop); attachment through lower ring?; reworking of ring	Possible mending (reverse)	Cremation burial (remains determined as female on unknown grounds)
O3	Freyr	Y	Whole surface ground	N	–	Broken arm, smoothing of stub	Stray find
O4	Warrior pendant/amulet Thor	Y	Obverse: polished; Reverse: polished, slight casting irregularities	Loop (reverse); holes (body)	Slight flattening (loop)	–	Cremation burial

(Continued)

Table 1. (Continued)

	Previous interpretation	Multistaged manufacture?	Polish	Attachment	Microwear	Breakage/mending	Deposition
O5	Valkyrie pendant/amulet; Aristocratic housewife	Y	Obverse: polished; Reverse: polished, slight casting irregularities	Loop (reverse); Hole (feet)	Crisp surface; Possible attachment wear (feet)	Broken loop	Chamber burial, determined as female based on grave goods, attached to reliquary?
O6	Valkyrie pendant/amulet	Y	Obverse/reverse: polished	Loop (reverse) Hole (feet)	Slight facet (loop); additional attachment through feet(?); edges well worn	–	Chamber burial
O7	Valkyrie pendant/amulet	Y	Reverse: rough	Loop (reverse)	No suspension wear (loop); crisp surface	–	Disturbed(?) boat burial (remains genetically determined as male)
O8	Valkyrie OR aristocratic housewife	Y	Obverse/reverse: polished	Loop (reverse)	Flattening (loop), contact with hard material	–	Hoard
O9	Frigg or Freya	Y	Obverse/reverse: polished	Loop (reverse)	Rounding (edges)	Broken loop; striations through loop	Cremation burial
O10	Valkyrie, Freya or Frigg	Y	Obverse/reverse: rough	Double loop (reverse)	No suspension wear (loop)	–	Stray find

long or in knots'; 'men usually wore trousers or had delineated legs'; 'couples are usually male-female' (Mannering 2017). While important as foundational research, we do see three issues with such categorisations. First, despite critical interventions (Back Danielsson 2007; Arwill-Nordbladh 2013a; Amundsen & Moen 2023), a binary-gender system is conventionally assumed, not critically examined. Second, to make these systems work, scholarship has acknowledged, then excluded, a significant number of 'ungendered' objects (e.g. Mannering 2017: 26–27). Finally, the warrants of 'often' and 'usually' tend to disappear in subsequent consideration. Consequently, we are left with somewhat self-affirming iconographic traits that gloss over complexity and contradiction. When objects that defy easy sex/gender classifications are excluded from analysis, representational frameworks can tie us into particular kinds of epistemes while suppressing others. This article thus seeks to ask other research questions to generate other types of knowledge.

Results: traces of engagement and the making of bodies

The results of our microwear and RTI analyses challenge and complement previous interpretations of iconic Viking artefacts, highlighting that such objects have affected, and been affected by, varied processes of engagement during manufacture and use. Four types of engagement emerge from our analyses: multistaged making; attachment and circulation; breakage and mending; and deposition.

Manufacture and multistaged decoration

The figures analysed were created through a combination of techniques including casting, polishing, engraving and stamping. Moulds for anthropomorphic objects are known from key Viking Age sites such as Birka, Sweden, and Ribe, Denmark (Deckers *et al.* 2021: 40). Moulds were ceramic and generally single use, being broken to extract the figure. Consequently, body-makers could produce related, but rarely identical, objects. At the casting stage, body-makers decided which traits to accentuate or suppress; among the 10 objects studied, facial features are generally less detailed, while garments are rendered in a more intricate manner. Possibly, facial features were deemed less important than the costume for the intended purpose of the object.

Eight of the objects analysed were cast in silver, a highly valued material for the Vikings. Acquisition of silver was a driving force in Viking raids and expansions; the metal was sourced mainly from Arabic dirhams that were melted to produce jewellery and other objects (Kershaw & Merkel 2022). The capacity to recycle and remake metals is integral to the biographies of these miniature bodies; gleaming objects from faraway lands ultimately stabilised into bodily forms. The process of metal body-making required complex assemblages (clay, fire, hammers, chisels) and involved the entire sensory apparatus, assessing colours, sounds and qualities of the smelt at different stages (Kuijpers 2008). Most of the objects studied here were presumably made by different hands, and different moulds, in order to rearticulate the human body in various forms and

substances. Yet, some seem to share histories of manufacture—perhaps making them ‘kin’ (Eriksen 2022).

The process of making did not finish with casting but entailed further steps, principally the use of abrasion (with progressively finer materials) to create smooth, shiny surfaces. Variation is apparent in the degree of polish between the obverse (front) and reverse (back) sides of the objects, and in the way in which grooves were enhanced. Figures O2, O6, O8 and O9 saw detailed polishing of both obverse and reverse sides, while some irregularities from casting are still visible on the reverse of O4 and O5, and O7 saw polish only on the obverse side. While such variations may be interpreted as varied levels of skill, they may also be linked to human-object intra-actions. Did polishing choices connect with how figures were intended to be displayed, and whether the reverse was expected to be visible? Or were traces of earlier stages of manufacture deliberately left as evidence for the processes of making associated with the figure?

The Rällinge figurine (O3) stands out in terms of making (Figure 3). Following casting, its surface was smoothed using an abrasive material, and chasing with a hammer and a punch was then used to define certain features, including grooves below the eyes and spirals on the back. Occasionally, the groove interiors were subsequently smoothed over and regularised using abrasion. The spiral decorations are not consistent in their execution, however. On the right shoulder, a double spiral is seemingly in the process of making, with one of the lines not fully chased. The opposite shoulder has only one spiral, while two curved lines rather than full spirals mark the lower back. The variable execution in these details may suggest that people engaged with the figure by adding elements at different times. The process of making, therefore, may have been extended, opening tantalising possibilities for how to understand the intra-actions among human and metal bodies. Rather than a linear sequence of actions (completion of manufacture, use), engagement with human maker(s) may have happened through multiple events.

Attachment, circulation, wrapping

For most of the objects examined here, scholarship has assumed that they were displayed as pendants or ‘amulets’ (e.g. Helmbrecht 2013; Deckers *et al.* 2021). Indeed, nine out of 10 objects display some form of suspension device—perforation through the object or loops on the reverse or on top of the object—indicating the capacity to be assembled with other objects and materials (conventionally assumed to be strings of beads, necklaces or other jewellery). They were thus (re)configurable and manipulable, able to enter in and out of different kinds of relations and collections. Only the Rällinge figurine was made without an obvious device for attachment.

To investigate potential attachments, we examined the attachment loops and perforations for microwear traces. Our results demonstrate a high degree of diversity in attachment rather than a homogenising interpretive function as ‘pendants’ (Figure 4). Three objects (O5, O7 & O10) show no traces of suspension from their attachment loops, indicating limited or no use as ‘pendants’.

However, two of the ‘valkyrie’ figures (O5 & O6) show facets in the gap between the feet, suggesting that the artefacts may have been fastened/suspended additionally/

Figure 3. Microwear traces on O3, the Rällinge figurine: A) manufacturing striations; B) groove below eye; C) incomplete spiral groove on the upper back; D) single curved line on the lower back (figure by C. Tsoraki; Rällinge photograph by O. Myrin, Swedish Historical Museums, CC BY 4.0).

alternatively at the ‘bottom’. Could these miniatures have been suspended upside down? Moreover, the loops of three objects were broken (O1, O5 & O9), though whether broken during use or after deposition is difficult to determine. Despite the break, O9 displays perpendicular striations through the loop on its reverse side. These striations do not seem to indicate suspension from a necklace, but instead give the impression of tight binding/wrapping against another object or material. Likewise, two objects display partial flattening of their attachment loops, suggesting that the figures were attached to

Figure 4. Micrographs showing examples of attachment devices (figure by C. Tzoraki).

hard materials, rather than being suspended against softer materials such as fabric or human flesh. A ubiquitous interpretation as objects of bodily adornment does not, therefore, fit with our results, raising the question of what else the figures may have been attached to—other metal objects, wooden structures (posts?) or other materials entirely (see below).

Traces of object circulation were also considered, again finding a high degree of diversity. Two of the ‘valkyries’ (O6 & O9) show substantial rounding of edges suggesting extensive handling over time. Long-term object curation in the Viking Age is apparent, for example, in the Aska burial, which contained O1 and O2 among an artefact assemblage spanning centuries of production (Arwill-Nordbladh 2012). The potential for multigenerational curation opens further horizons for the intra-actions miniature bodies may have seen, of long-term or interweaving storage, display and wear. The rounded edges of O6 and O9 may stem, for example, from fabric wrapped around the surface of the figures or from their storage in pouches, challenging the idea that their primary function was display. Wrapping or ‘dressing’ anthropomorphic imagery in fabric is a specific form of intra-acting with miniature bodies that finds parallels in broadly contemporaneous gold-foil figures (Back Danielsson 2013) and the so-called Buddha from Helgö (Gyllensvär 2004: fig. 4). These examples testify to the dressing of anthropomorphic bodies through the addition of gold props, such as belts and necklaces, and leather arm- and neck-rings, respectively. While the exact nature is difficult to pinpoint, it seems clear that some artefacts demanded regular engagement.

The miniscule size of many of the artefacts also casts doubt on whether visual engagement was their primary purpose (cf. Bailey 2014; Weismantel 2014; Eriksen 2022). How visible, for example, would the Rällinge spirals be in a world without cameras and microscopes; could they only be experienced under certain conditions (e.g. lit at a specific angle, or through touch)? Microwear on the chin of the Aska head (O1) may hint at repeated rubbing or handling (and the importance of touch), though no such traces were found on the Aska pregnant body (O2), despite previous speculation (Arwill-Nordbladh 2013b: 415).

In contrast to the well-rounded presentation and potential long-term curation of O6 and O9, O4 and O5 present crisp edges and were thus used sparingly or even made shortly before deposition. Might they have been made for deposition, rather than for use as bodily adornment? Perhaps some objects were neither to be suspended from a body or object, nor manipulated through wrapping or handling—perhaps they were always meant to accompany the dead.

Breaking and mending bodies

Two of the miniature bodies have undergone further forms of manipulation in terms of breakage. The Rällinge figure (O3) is missing part of its left arm. Though we cannot say whether this break was accidental or intentional, the upper fractured end of the arm has a bevel near the missing part, suggesting that the place of breakage was reworked (Figure 5). Likewise, the lower fractured end is smoothed but this may be affected by

Figure 5. Traces of reworking on the Rällinge figurine (figure by C. Tsoraki; Rällinge photograph by O. Myrin, Swedish Historical Museums, CC BY 4.0).

have been taken to smooth the edges after breaking the object. Perhaps it did not matter, or perhaps its decapitation was an important part of the object biography, rendering the traces of this action visible.

Deposition

Ultimately, at some point the decision was made to take these objects out of circulation, moving them from whatever prior relationships they were engaged with to new locations and situations. The majority (six out of 10) were deposited in burials—that is, they were to be associated with human remains, as well as an assemblage of artefacts. The others were deposited in hoards or are stray finds.

The practice of linking anthropomorphic objects with dead bodies through burials is little remarked upon in the literature as the objects carry an *a priori* association with personal adornment reflecting ‘wealth’ or ‘(ritual) status’. Yet, selecting artefacts to accompany the dead rather than circulating them as heirlooms or through systems of gift exchange is a highly intentional act. Why, at this moment, was the object taken out of the world of the living? Why did it belong with *this* specific dead body? What kinds of engagements were changing, cut off or made new at the moment of deposition? While we may never be able to answer these questions in full, moving from objects as static ‘symbols’ of deities or status, and thinking more deeply about the social fabric

patination/corrosion. However the breaks occurred, care was taken to rework the upper (and perhaps also the lower) fracture and to smooth the stumps. Furthermore, the choice not to mend or replace the broken arm, but to smooth the place of the fracture instead, seems deliberate.

The second object that has seen further manipulation is the Aska head (O1) interpreted as the mount of a *völva* staff (Price 2019: 104). However, it seems the head was originally attached to a body—it was not cast as a detached head from the beginning. Strikingly, here we found evidence for active percussion at the base of the head (Figure 6), meaning that at some stage of the object’s history, it was actively and intentionally decapitated and thereby split into two objects.

What happened to the rest of the metal body, and how it may have originally looked, we do not know. In contrast to the Rällinge figure, little care seems to

Figure 6. Microwear traces on the Aska head: A–B) percussive traces at the base of the head; C) smooth finishing on the interior ridge of the chin (figure by C. Tsoraki; Aska photograph by O. Myrin, Swedish Historical Museums, CC BY 4.0).

they were part of, centres them in practice and in affective relations rather than as passive objects of ‘art’ or ‘ritual’.

The placement of artefacts in burials may speak to their intra-action. The O5 ‘valkyrie’ was found in the midsection of a burial, alongside beads, a cross and a miniature chair and shield. Original documentation indicates that it was found attached to another silver artefact, interpreted as a silver reliquary (Arbman 1940: 298–300). While the publication notes this attachment as likely accidental, we see little reason to outright dismiss the original observation (Figure 7). If this was the original mode of deposition, it raises two interesting observations: first, we may here have an example of how some ‘amulets’ could be attached to hard surfaces/other objects (possibly upside down); second, the combination of Christian and pre-Christian artefacts provides further richness and nuance in our understanding of how these objects may have been worlded.

Figure 7. Location of O5 in the burial at Birka, and an interpretation of the object attached to a reliquary (figure by M.H. Eriksen; grave drawing from Arbman 1940: 299).

remains securely sexed as female; while two have been gendered female based on the assessment of grave-goods (which comes with its own biases). Meanwhile, O7—a gilded ‘valkyrie’ figurine—was found with human remains osteologically and genetically sexed as male (Arrhenius 1990; Rodríguez-Varela *et al.* 2023: e4), challenging the assumption that these objects are exclusively connected with women’s bodies. Even when biological sex can be genetically or osteologically estimated, we cannot assume that this was *the* causal connection linking the human and object bodies, nor is—famously—deposition in death the same as use in life. Linked assumptions about these objects seem to steer interpretations. Thus, taking a step back and allowing the objects to emerge, rather than forcing them into assumed categories, allows us to see them in a new light.

Discussion

The first objective of this study was to explore through microwear and imaging analyses the engagement of 10 Viking anthropomorphic objects. Rather than studying these merely as objects to be visually appraised and categorised from afar, we asked: in what ways did these objects intra-act with the world? Microwear and imaging analyses provide key new evidence for four types of engagement: multistaged making; attachment and circulation; breakage and mending; and deposition.

Significantly, our analyses reveal that the making of these anthropomorphs was a multistaged process. Tiny metal bodies were not made, once and for all, and then visually appraised, like museum pieces. They were in an ongoing process of being made (cf. Tsoraki *et al.* 2023), and that process may have been a key form of human/object intra-action. Our results raise new questions, and although these may never be answered

The placement of O5 in the burial does support its use for bodily adornment; however, three objects were found in cremation burials. In these cases, the metal bodies cannot have been burnt on the pyre with the human body as an object of personal adornment, as the silver would have melted. Rather, the artefacts—if indeed used by the dead—would necessarily have been removed from the body before burning and reunited with it after, and were thus intentionally preserved intact, in contrast to the human remains transformed through fire.

Finally, we explore the *a priori* assumption that the ‘valkyrie’ figures were uniquely connected to women’s bodies. None of the burials that contained the objects examined here include skeletal

completely, they nevertheless provide impetus for further research. Can we assume that one crafter would execute all parts of the casting and multistaged decoration? Was a multistaged process an integral part of body-making, rather than the creation of a ‘final’ metal body as soon as possible?

Analyses of attachments and microwear indicate substantial variation in object use-life. Rather than visually categorising artefacts as ‘amulets’ or ‘valkyrie pendants’, we demonstrate that type-like objects engaged the world in diverse ways. Some clearly circulated through hands and situations over long periods of time, while others may have been made specifically for deposition. Some may have adorned human bodies, others may have been wrapped in fabric or attached to hard materials—for example, [Figure 7](#)’s upside-down ‘valkyrie’ attached to a Christian reliquary. Overall, there is significant variability in how artefacts were used, touched, displayed or concealed.

Two objects are broken (at least one intentionally). This adds to existing discourse on intentionally broken objects such as swords and brooches, discussed by Ratican (2024) as ritually modified. Such breakage additionally provides a tantalising glimpse into shared motifs between human and miniature bodies: their capacities to fragment into ‘body-objects’. In the Body-Politics project from which this article stems, we are also examining human remains deposited in settlement contexts from the Iron and Viking Ages. This dataset is mostly made up by single skeletal elements, frequently cranial elements, that have intentionally been broken apart from the rest of the human body and deposited in and around dwellings (cf. Eriksen 2020). It is striking that both metal bodies and bodies of flesh and blood were intentionally broken through specific forms of intra-action, potentially speaking to a social significance of body-worldings where the body was partible and transformational.

Our second objective in this article was to trouble the way scholarship has enforced gender and other categories in the interpretation of these artefacts; which can have transferable value for other periods and places. Assumptions about value, amuletic function and gender norms permeate these interpretations. We cannot assume single-gendered use of these, or other, objects without first building robust arguments, nor can we assume that all objects were at all times used for (female) bodily adornment. Perhaps our most crucial result is that the traces of making, using and engagement clearly demonstrate that different objects did different things. The grouping of artefacts lies beyond visual-representational dimensions; they were equally (or even more so) defined by what they did, and how they intra-acted with other human and nonhuman bodies. Indeed, in some ways breakable metal bodies functioned more similarly to certain fleshy, human bodies than they did to type-like artefacts: suggesting typologies in action that cut across human-nonhuman divides.

Conclusion

Iconic anthropomorphic objects, key to arguments about Nordic pre-Christian religion and magical practices, can provide insights beyond their imposed categorical associations if we ask new questions of them. By moving our gaze from what the objects *symbolise* to how they intra-acted with the world, we have generated new evidence for the practices

and choices of body-making, the diversity of attachment beyond body adornment, indicating that the function of the objects should at times be reassessed, and the intentional breaking and mending of small metal bodies, echoing how human bodies could be fractured and broken. Ultimately, we argue that this approach has allowed the objects to inform us, rather than the other way around.

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Data availability statement

Data are available as supplementary materials.

Online supplementary material (OSM)

To view supplementary material for this article, please visit the zenodo data repository at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15852731>

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